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Teaching Language Effects on Students' Performance on Midlist Student*

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ABSTRACT

We announce our findings on the success and connection of our medical student to the language of teaching. We used the strength definition inventory (FCI) as our research aid and provided it to our students in class on test materials before and after guidance. The primary language of our students is Arabic and we teach in English. Thus, both Arabic and English have been checked. This research is one aspect of a broader effort to examine our department's whole instructional mechanism (teaching and learning). The low English skills of the students were seen in the classroom. Our findings show that the output and the vocabulary used by the subject were weakly associated.

INTRODUCTION

The findings we present in this paper derive from the research that we began analysing at the university as part of a new project (Bani-Salameh (2016), 4). This section of the research was prompted by feedback from our teachers (not necessarily in physics) about very low English skills in students. The instructor, makes the students keen on what is being taught. Consequently, a student's progress in an EFL program is enhanced significantly (Rashid H., et. all (2020)). In order to verify if the student performs otherwise, the aim is to have a well-defined regular exam in both their languages and in English. One of the factors for our decision was the variety of subjects addressed by the exam, we are teaching students the same subjects and have already learned these problems at secondary

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school. This research involves the force definition inventory. Therefore, students should be conscious and hopefully perform well on the exam of these general basic physics principles. The exam was offered to students two times, both in Arabic and in English before guidance in school on the topics of the exam and after the examination. The system makes a clear student analysis of results in two distinct dimensions: one is linked to language effects and the other to the continuation of these effects following instruction in English. Our purpose is to measure the impact of language on the success of students if the language of teaching is different from their own. The other aim is to assess the success of our English instruction in improving their efficiency. We explain our teaching methods briefly below and how data in Section 2 is gathered and assessed. Section 3 discusses the findings and comments and the final part of this review devotes itself to our conclusions.

Data Collection

Premedical and pre-healing students were listed in our physics curriculum for health education. Students interested in this research. Both students learned Arabic in their first year of study, as a first language. Their English abilities varied from outstanding to very low (which was just a limited percentage). Even though our class is given to students in the second half of the first semester, the overwhelming majority of our students have always missed the English skills required to develop their English skills. This created a problem for us to teach physics in English quite challenging to think about; are we teaching English or physics? Our goal was to teach English as easy as possible so that the majority of students could learn. This research included three separate classes, each with a total of 60 students. We only included data of the students who completed both exams in order to allow a reasonable clear distinction between the outcomes of the before and after test; 152 were included. The same teacher instructed all three parts so that the learning settings could prevent any variations. Material has been addressed and explored similarly, the same intensity and the same examples have been discussed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Before we begin our review of the findings we should point out that the FCI students' overall poor output has been recorded around the world.^{1,4,8-11} As seen in table 1. This vulnerability, reasons or remedies are not in the focus of this specific study and will no longer be addressed. Our key purpose in this document is to research the impact of the language on the success of students. We wanted students to be much better off on the exam when we began this research. When we began this research, we thought that students would perform in their own language even better. This assumption was founded on the fact that most students had low English skills and that their constant questions (from assignments, surveys or tests) were difficult to understand because they were written in French, and if the exam was in Arabic they could do better. The findings in Table 1 demonstrate to our delight that there is no output difference that is contingent on the test language.

On the opposite, after the English exam students performed higher than after the Arabic examination. Looking at the details provided in Table 1, we can see that students score in pre-tests nearly identically; the mean FCI results are 27.1% in Arabic and 26.5% in English. In the normal error of the mean and it's trivial the gap between mean values. This is an indicator of no influence on student success in the vocabulary used in the exam. The post-test findings reveal stronger test outcomes (mean score of 37.3 percent) than the Arabic equivalent of the English study.

The results of this experiment are common to determine the normalized benefit of Hake 4 to assess the quality of orders. The effects of that test are used to estimating Hake's normalized gain 4. In the post-English examination, we will use this formula here to calculate improved output as results in both pre-tests was identical. The standardized benefit of Hake is determined by an equation that considers the pre- and post-test scores and calculates the benefit in success normally described by the directions provided to students between the two exams. In the English variant of the exam, Hake's standardized benefit stood at 14.8 percent, about 1.5 times the benefit of the Arabic edition (10.4 percent). The FCI exam we used contains 30 questions, so students could (by average) respond to two more questions in the English version of the examination, as compared to in Arabic. We should also remember that these improvements are considered to be poor indicating little improvement in the success of our students,

as in the case of Hake and Viiri studies.^{12,13} Our two other reported project reports providing in-depth details on our results are listed to interested readers.

We present in Fig to get a closer look at the success of students in these exams. 1 number of students who correctly respond to each object in the inventory (normalized to the total number of students). When the fig is carefully studied. 1, one understands easily that a definite winner is challenging to draw a firm conclusion.

We may note that students in some of the test Arabic version mentioned in certain questions were slightly better than comparable questions in their English version by proportion of the correct answers for each of the 30 questions in the FCI exam, both in Arabic and in English, in the pre-test (up) and post-test (down) exams. And in a few other questions we note minimal production in the English edition. This confirms our earlier inference from the mean findings on comparable outcomes in both pre-test models. Looking at post-tests, in the English version of the test we can prove improved results. In nearly all questions in the English edition we see higher percentages of students obtaining the right answer than in the Arabic edition. This surprising discovery may have several causes and it would be very hard to determine one explanation. The fact that our directions are in English may also be one of the factors which reminds or forces students to learn the English terminology required to understand the issues in the exam. Both students have learned these principles in physics at one time before, mostly in Arabic, some in English, so (ideally speaking) knowing the issue is just what prevents students from receiving the correct answer. The teaching of the English language to students in this situation would allow them to better score in the English, but not in Arabic edition of the exam. Fear is a negative emotion that can help you learn to be effective, 2. There is of course a great risk that the students' mind will be mistaken and they may still respond incorrectly even though they understand the issue. We researched these misunderstandings and recorded a complete list in a previous work.^{1, 4} the way they are trained in Arabic and what they have been learned is other reasons that may lead to the disparity in quality. We never know if the physics definition they have studied in Arabic is correct. They never had an ability to address mistakes in Arabic in this class and therefore fared worse than in the English language edition. Our English lessons, on the other hand, may have helped certain students learn physics principles and some other students fix current misunderstandings. This may have tended to boost the students' success in the English edition of the exam.

CONCLUSIONS

Our analysis aimed at evaluating the impact on student success of the learning language. We thought that if students were evaluated in their own language (Arabic), they could do more. In order to allow the distinction, we twice evaluated our students in two versions: one in Arabic and the other in English, as usual, in this field of research (FCI). To our surprise, the success of the students was not influenced by the test language in the pretests and, to add to our surprise, in the post tests they were much more successful in the English edition. One main inference is: that is the explanation why students are slow in this general class and in this specific test cannot be the language other than their

own. We believe anything to refer to our physics students can also be applicable in other areas of science and we look forward to collaborating with our fellow students to assess this. The study earned no specific support from federal, private or non-profit funding organizations.

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